

XRD and SEM Analysis, and Semiconductor Type Determination of TiO₂ for Dye-sensitized Solar Cell

Soe Myat*, Than Htay*, San Nyein Khine**, Kyaw San Oo*, Tin Hla Yin*, Tin Tin Mya*,
Khin Phyu Phyu Tun*

*Department of Physics, Sittway University

**Faculty of Computer System and Technology, University of Computer Studies-Sittway

Abstract— Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is a wide band-gap n-type semiconductor. Anatase TiO₂ is the most common structure used in high performance dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC). Nanoporous TiO₂ serves double-duty as an electron acceptor and a scaffold to hold large numbers of dye molecules in DSSC. The porosity of TiO₂ is a key feature as it has roughly a thousand times greater a surface area than the equivalent flat area. In this work, TiO₂ crystallite size (43.55 nm) has been calculated by using XRD data, and the morphology and the grain-size of TiO₂ (average grain size of 0.2 μm ~ 0.3 μm) with different solvents have been also studied by SEM.

Index Terms— Anatase, DSSC, SEM, TCO, TiO₂, XRD.

I. INTRODUCTION

Large amount of carbon dioxide emission by the combustion of fossil fuel leads to serious environmental problem such as the global warming. Solar energy is regarded as one of the perfect clean energy resources. Because the amount of solar energy reaching the surface of the earth is about 10,000 times larger than worldwide energy consumption. So, there would be no worry for the energy supply line even if a small fraction of sunlight could be converted to alternative and usable energy forms.

Devices that will permit direct conversion of sunlight to electricity are called photovoltaic solar cells. But the price of the first and second generation photovoltaic cells exceeds that from the traditional fossil fuel. So, dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC) has been regarded as the most prospective clean energy source. DSSC consists of four main parts such as TiO₂ (electron acceptor), dye sensitizer (photochemical pumping device), redox electrolyte (electron donor) and carbon layer (catalyst)^{[1][3][5-7]}.

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is cheap, abundant, nontoxic and biocompatible, and anatase TiO₂ is the low temperature stable form and it gives mesoscopic films that are transparent and colorless^[11]. DSSCs are able to work under cloudy skies and non-direct sunlight, and also used indoor. Dr. blade technique, screen printing, spin coating, spray pyrolysis, electrochemical deposition and gas phase deposition can be used to deposit TiO₂ colloidal on transparent conducting oxide (TCO) layer of glass electrode. Nanoporous TiO₂ used in this work, has double-duty: (i) a scaffold to hold large numbers of dye molecules and (ii) an electron acceptor. ZnO, Fe₂O₃, SnO₂, CdSe, CdS, etc can be used as electron acceptor in DSSC^{[4][11][12]}.

X-ray diffractometry is mainly used for the identification and qualification of the samples by their diffraction patterns. The sample is placed in the centre of goniometer. After that it is scanned through an angle 2θ from 10° to 70° and the diffracted X-rays enter the detector, and then the data are recorded. These data produce their respective diffraction patterns which are identified by JCPDS (Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards) files. So, XRD is a useful technique to investigate the crystal structure, the Miller indices (h k l) and the lattice parameters (a, b, c) of the sample studied. By using the Miller indices and the lattice parameters, the interplanar spacing can be evaluated and then the crystallite size can also be calculated by Scherrer formula^{[2][9]}.

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is one of the most versatile instruments available for the examination and the analysis of the microstructural characteristics of solid objects. This is because it can provide high resolution image of the material. Sharply focused high-energy electrons scan over the surface of specimens, and signals can be classed as secondary electrons, backscattered electrons, characteristic X-rays, and auger electrons. Photographic images of various energies can be obtained. SEM can be directly used to observe the surface micro-structures. Its magnifications are from 10 to 200000 or more^[8]. Fig. 1.1 shows the structure of TiO₂ based DSSC.

Fig. 1.1 Structure of TiO₂ based dye-sensitized solar cell

II. BACKGROUND THEORY

2.1. X-ray Diffractometry (XRD)

XRD can be used to investigate the crystal structure of the sample studied. By using the following formula, the interplanar spacing can be evaluated for tetragonal structure.

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \left[\frac{h^2 + k^2}{a^2} \right] + \frac{l^2}{c^2}$$

where d = interplanar spacing
 a, c = lattice parameters
 (h k l) = Miller indices

This is Bragg's law formula. Bragg's law action is shown in Fig 2.1.

$$2d \sin \theta = n\lambda$$

where n = 1
 d = interplanar spacing
 θ = diffraction angle of the peak
 λ = wavelength of incident X-ray

The lattice parameters a and c for tetragonal structure can be calculated by

$$\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{c^2(h^2 + k^2) + a^2 l^2} = \frac{\lambda^2}{4a^2 c^2}$$

where λ = wavelength of incident X-ray
 θ = diffraction angle of the peak

X-ray diffractometer used in this work with the wavelength of 1.54056 Å of copper target, is shown in Fig 2.2^[2].

Fig. 2.1 Bragg's law action

Fig. 2.2 X-ray diffractometer (XRD)

The following is the Scherrer formula used to calculate the crystallite size.

$$t = \frac{0.9\lambda}{B \cos \theta}$$

where t = thickness of the crystallites (nm)
 λ = wavelength of incident X-ray (nm)
 θ = diffraction angle of the peak under

consideration at FWHM (°)
 B = observed FWHM (radians)

2.2. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM is one of the more useful instruments to examine and analyze the microstructure of the materials. In the present work, morphological features of anatase TiO₂ powders were investigated by using JEOL JSM-5610LV SEM with secondary electron imaging (SEI) and backscattered electron imaging (BEI), and 10,000 times of photo-magnification. Schematic diagram and scanning electron microscope (SEM) are shown in Fig 2.3 and Fig 2.4 respectively.

Fig. 2.3 Schematic diagram of SEM

Fig. 2.4 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

2.3. Semiconductor Type Determination of TiO₂

The hot point probe method has been used to determine the conductivity type of the semiconductor. In semiconductor, there are two types of majority carriers: electron and positive hole. In n-type semiconductor, the majority carrier is electron and hole for p-type. The hot point probe set-up is shown in Fig 2.5. Firstly, the hot soldering gun tip is connected to the positive probe of the multi-meter. The sign of the voltage polarity defines the type of the semiconductor whether n-type or p-type. Due to the hot positive point probe, electrons move away from the hot point and the polarity of the thermal voltage

shows positive value. Similarly, the majority carriers of p-type semiconductor: holes move away from the point due to the hot point. So, the polarity shows negative.

Fig. 2.5 Hot point probe set-up

III. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

3.1. XRD Study

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns of TiO₂ is shown in Fig 3.1. XRD data of diffraction angle (2θ), atomic spacing (d), Miller indices (hkl), Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) and Peak height (%) of the sample are tabulated in Table 3.1. The collected XRD lines of TiO₂ are (101), (103), (004), (112), (200), (105), (211), (204) and (116). They are found to agree with the standard data of Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS). The appearance of these diffraction peaks demonstrates that TiO₂ possesses tetragonal (anatase), shown in Fig 3.1. The lattice parameters are a = b = 3.7577 Å and c = 9.5227 Å. By using FWHM (B), θ and λ, the crystallite size of TiO₂ can be calculated. But FWHM(B)(degree) needs to be converted into FWHM(B)(radian).

Fig. 3.1 XRD pattern of TiO₂

The crystallite size of TiO₂ is 43.55 nm. The nanoporous structure of TiO₂ layer suggests that the roughness factor of

1000 is achievable while the particle size of TiO₂ is less than 50 nm. In other words, 1 cm² coated area of the conductive transparent electrode with nanostructured TiO₂ layer actually possessing a surface area of 1000 cm². In this work, the crystallite size of TiO₂ is about 43.55 nm and dye staining area of TiO₂ is about 1000 cm².

TABLE 3.1. XRD Data of TiO₂

Line No:	2θ (°)	(hkl)	d (Å)	FWHM (o)	Height (%)
1	25.643	(101)	3.4711	0.185	100.0
2	37.265	(103)	2.4100	0.154	7.6
3	38.140	(004)	2.357	0.157	26.8
4	38.898	(112)	2.3134	0.184	8.1
5	48.397	(200)	1.8792	0.146	41.4
6	54.221	(105)	1.6903	0.159	22.7
7	55.364	(211)	1.6581	0.123	27.3
8	62.986	(204)	1.4745	0.140	20.2
9	69.074	(116)	1.3587	0.136	9.6

3.2. SEM Study

SEM has been employed for the characterization of morphology of TiO₂ powder. Fig 3.2, Fig 3.3 and Fig 3.4 show the SEM images of TiO₂(raw), TiO₂(H₂O₂) and TiO₂(HNO₃) respectively. The porosity of TiO₂ is essential not only to ensure high roughness factor, but also to enhance the penetration of the redox couples into film. According to the SEM images, TiO₂ with HNO₃ has larger porosity than that with H₂O₂. TiO₂ is composed of interconnected spherical shaped particles with an average grain size in the range 0.2 μm ~ 0.3 μm. Most of the TiO₂ powders are uniform with clear grain boundary.

Fig. 3.2 SEM image of TiO₂ (raw)

Fig. 3.3 SEM image of TiO₂ (H₂O₂)

Fig. 3.4 SEM image of TiO₂ (HNO₃)

3.3. n-type Semiconductor TiO₂

According to the literature, TiO₂ is wide band-gap n-type semiconductor with band-gap energy 3.2 eV. So the hot point probe method has been used to determine the type of the semiconductor whether p-type or n-type. On the other hand, the conductivity type (plus or minus) has been studied by the hot point probe method. The hot soldering gun tip is connected to the positive probe of the multi-meter first. And then the measurements can be made as shown in Fig 3.7. The polarity of TiO₂ thermal voltage is positive in Table 3.2. It means that the majority carriers (electrons in n-type) moves away from the point in which the high temperature probe of voltmeter exists and the polarity of the thermal voltage shows positive value. So, TiO₂ in this work is n-type semiconductor.

Fig. 3.8 Positive polarity of TiO₂

TABLE 3.2. n-type semiconductor TiO₂

Sample	Thermal voltage (V _t)	Semiconductor type
TiO ₂	+9 mV	n-type semiconductor

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 XRD and SEM Results

Anatase and rutile are two crystalline forms of TiO₂ (the third form, brookite, is difficult to obtain). From XRD data, TiO₂ is anatase form of tetragonal structure with crystallite size of 43.55 nm and the lattice parameters are a = b = 3.7577Å and c = 9.5227Å. To increase the dye adsorbing area on TiO₂, the crystallite size of TiO₂ needs to be as small as possible. Therefore, P-25 commercial TiO₂ powder should be used to achieve small crystallite size. Moreover, TiO₂ (rutile)

has larger crystallite size than anatase. So, TiO₂ (anatase) is suitable to use for the high performance of DSSC. The size of TiO₂ with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) becomes slightly greater than that of TiO₂ with HNO₃ as shown in SEM images. In addition, it was found that TiO₂ layer with H₂O₂ can easily peel off from TCO glass after sintering at 450°C. So, HNO₃ (pH 3-4 in deionized water) should be used as the solvent for TiO₂ suspension. According to the hot point probe method, TiO₂ is n-type semiconductor. So TiO₂ is a wide band-gap n-type semiconductor with cheap, abundant, nontoxic and biocompatible. And then TiO₂ gives transparent and colourless mesoscopic film. So TiO₂ based DSSC can be able to work under cloudy skies and non-direct sunlight, and also used indoor. According to SEM data, the average grain size of TiO₂ is in the range of 0.2 μm ~ 0.3 μm^[10]. And then TiO₂ have clear grain boundary and uniform shape.

V. CONCLUSION

In XRD pattern, (hkl) planes: (101), (103), (004), (112), (200), (105), (211), (204) and (116) show that TiO₂ has tetragonal (anatase) structure. The crystallite size of less than 100 nm is suitable for a scaffold to hold large number of dye molecules.

As shown in SEM images, TiO₂ with solvent HNO₃ has larger porosity than that with solvent H₂O₂. Large porosity gives high roughness factor to stain the large number of dye molecules and to penetrate the redox couples into the film. According to the hot point probe method, positive polarity of TiO₂, in Fig 3.8, shows n-type semiconductor.

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AUTHORS

First Author – Soe Myat, Associate Professor in Physics, Sittway University, Myanmar and email address- soemyatsul@gmail.com.

Second Author – Than Htay, Professor, Head of the Department of Physics, Sittway University, Myanmar and email address- drthanhtay44@email.com.

Third Author – San Nyein Khine, Associate Professor, Faculty of Computer System and Technology, University of Computer Studies-Sittway, Myanmar and email address- sannyeinkhaing969@gmail.com.

Fourth Author – Kyaw San Oo, Lecturer, Department of Physics, Sittway University, Myanmar and email address- kyawsanoo1431@email.com.

Fifth Author – Tin Hla Yin, Lecturer, Department of Physics, Sittway University, Myanmar and email address- dawtinhlain11@gmail.com.

Sixth Author – Tin Tin Mya, Lecturer, Department of Physics, Sittway University, Myanmar and email address- tintinmya19@gmail.com.

Seventh Author – Khin Phyu Phyu Tun, Lecturer, Department of Physics, Sittway University, Myanmar and email address- phyu4952@gmail.com.